

Research Article

Empowering Digital Marketing Among B40 Entrepreneurs in Kelantan Through E-Module Affiliate Program

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Abstract: *The empowerment of digital marketing among B40 entrepreneurs through the e-Module Affiliate Program is critical in enhancing their business opportunities and elevating their socio-economic status. This program is designed to equip underprivileged entrepreneurs, particularly those in the B40 group, with essential skills in digital marketing, with a specific focus on affiliate marketing strategies. An e-module on affiliate marketing is a teaching tool intended to show entrepreneurs how to make money from promoting goods or services for businesses via affiliate networks. It often consists of a range of components, such as assignments, video lectures, and textual educational materials, all aimed at assisting entrepreneurs in understanding the concepts and procedures of affiliate marketing. By doing this, entrepreneurs become less dependent on traditional marketing channels and get access to internet networks that enable them to communicate with customers anywhere worldwide. This paper highlights the significant effects of the e-Module Affiliate Program in terms of increased sales, improved business sustainability, and more powerful digital literacy among participants through a case study of members of the B40 community in Kelantan, Malaysia. The results demonstrate a significant increase in the participant's capacity to make money via digital channels, demonstrating the value of affiliate marketing in assisting low-income entrepreneurs in achieving economic empowerment. The effect of the E-Modul Affiliate Program on the entrepreneurial attempts of B40 participants in Kelantan is investigated in this study. The research evaluates the program's effectiveness in raising participants' income levels by boosting their digital marketing skills, increasing the exposure of their digital companies, and utilizing a mixed-methods approach that includes surveys, interviews, and case studies. Based on initial results, individuals who actively participated in the E-Modul had significant improvements in their understanding of digital marketing strategies and could implement these methods into practice to expand their business and increase their income.*

Keywords: digital marketing, B40 entrepreneurs, affiliate marketing, E-Module, digital literacy,

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1. INTRODUCTION

Digital marketing has become an essential tool for modern businesses, offering unparalleled opportunities for growth and expansion. Unfortunately, many entrepreneurs have difficulty accessing and efficiently using these tools, particularly those from the B40 income group, which represents the lowest 40% of household earnings in Malaysia. Limited resources, a lack of digital literacy, and a lack of awareness of advanced marketing methods limit their capacity to compete in the ever-changing digital economy. In response to these challenges, the Empowering Digital Marketing Among B40 Entrepreneurs through the E-Module Affiliate Program was developed as a targeted initiative to bridge the digital divide and promote economic empowerment. The program is designed to equip B40 entrepreneurs with essential skills in digital marketing, particularly affiliate marketing, to help them grow their businesses, increase their income, and become more financially independent. The introduction of this program represents a significant effort to uplift the B40 community by providing them with the tools needed to succeed in the digital economy. The program focuses not only on teaching the technical aspects of digital marketing but also on fostering a mindset of entrepreneurship, creativity, and long-term business sustainability. This paper explores the structure, implementation, and outcomes of the e-Module Affiliate Program, highlighting its impact on B40 entrepreneurs in terms of business growth, digital literacy, and income generation. Through this program, the B40 entrepreneurs gain the ability to steer clear of the competitive digital market, take charge of their company's destiny, and make significant contributions to their local communities.

Ahmad & Ahmad (2019) said that digital marketing strategies, such as social media marketing, search engine optimization (SEO), email marketing, and affiliate marketing, provide powerful tools for business growth. Studies show that small businesses leveraging digital marketing can achieve significant growth and brand recognition even with limited budgets (Ahmad & Ahmad, 2019). For entrepreneurs in rural areas like Kelantan, digital platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and e-commerce websites can create opportunities to reach national and international markets.

According to Lim, a key barrier for B40 entrepreneurs adopting digital marketing is their lack of knowledge and skills. Effective interventions, such as training programs, workshops, and digital tools, can empower these entrepreneurs to use online platforms effectively (Lim, 2021).

According to Ali, e-modules are interactive, self-paced learning tools designed to enhance digital literacy. Studies have shown that e-learning when tailored to the specific needs of its target audience, can significantly improve digital competencies among low-income groups (Ali et al., 2020). The e-module affiliate program, in this context, can help B40 entrepreneurs in Kelantan gain the necessary skills to participate in affiliate marketing.

Nasharudin said that affiliate marketing allows businesses to collaborate with affiliates, who promote their products or services in exchange for a commission on sales. This model minimizes upfront costs, making it a viable strategy for low-income entrepreneurs. Studies indicate that affiliate marketing is an effective way to drive traffic and increase sales, especially for businesses with limited capital for extensive marketing campaigns (Nasharudin, 2020).

Empowering B40 entrepreneurs in Kelantan through digital marketing is crucial for fostering economic growth, improving livelihoods, and reducing poverty. The e-module affiliate program is an intensive program designed to give these entrepreneurs the abilities and information they need to contribute successfully to the digital economy. The training program offers a low-cost, scalable approach to business by fusing affiliate marketing opportunities with instruction in digital marketing.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 *e-module content*

E-Module content was developed to fulfill the objective of the study by enhancing the step-by-step affiliate program instructions. Digital sources and printed hard copies can be distributed to entrepreneurs to develop their marketing skills.

Based on Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick Digital Marketing Fundamentals is an introduction to digital marketing, covering topics such as social media marketing, search engine optimization (SEO), email marketing, and online advertising to help entrepreneurs build a strong foundation in digital marketing (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019).

Heidari said Affiliate Marketing Guide: Step-by-step instructions on how affiliate marketing works, its benefits, and how to choose suitable affiliate programs (Heidari, 2020).

According to Loh, Yee, and Chen Tools and Platforms are the method of Tutorials on using key digital marketing platforms (e.g., Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Google Ads, Shopee, Lazada) and affiliate networks. Training modules focused on popular e-commerce platforms like Shopee, and Lazada, and social media platforms like Facebook and Instagram, which have proven to be effective in Malaysia (Loh, Yee, & Chen, 2021).

2.2 *Training Workshops*

Training workshops are delivered by professional facilitators teams from different fields such as business and management, accountancy, information technology, languages, Islamic experts, and art and design. Training workshop sessions are held in different venues based on the entrepreneur's location and selected participants. The supervision session will take place after the training workshops done by monitoring the entrepreneurs for progress of implementing the skills and knowledge of digital marketing.

According to Rahman et al. (2022), In-Person and Virtual Sessions will conduct hands-on workshops to teach B40 entrepreneurs how to use digital platforms, create content, and run affiliate marketing campaigns. These can be held in local community centers or virtually, teaching entrepreneurs to create and manage social media profiles, run affiliate marketing campaigns, and use e-commerce platforms (Rahman et al., 2022).

Khalid & Baharudin said that Peer-to-Peer Learning plays an important role as a mentorship model where more experienced digital marketers mentor will monitor the new entrepreneurs. Peer-based learning is effective in community-based entrepreneurship programs (Khalid & Baharudin, 2021).

E-Modul Delivery based on Shahrudin is given that most B40 entrepreneurs access the internet via smartphones, the e-module must be mobile-friendly to maximize accessibility (Shahrudin et al., 2021).

Online Learning Platform: A user-friendly platform where entrepreneurs can access the e-module, watch tutorial videos, and connect with mentors and other participants (Muntean, 2018).

Affiliate Program Integration: Collaborate with local businesses and national brands to enable B40 entrepreneurs to market products via affiliate programs. This is especially useful for entrepreneurs who cannot invest in inventory (Heidari, 2020).

Ongoing Support and Monitoring: Regular webinars and workshops should be organized to update entrepreneurs on the latest trends in digital marketing and affiliate programs (Chaffey & Ellis-Chadwick, 2019). Set up help desks or support groups through messaging platforms like WhatsApp and Telegram where entrepreneurs can seek assistance (Rahman et al., 2022).

Collaboration with Government and Non-Governmental organizations will assist the entrepreneurs in offering microloans or grants to B40 business owners so they can finance digital marketing initiatives (Amin et al. 2020). Collaborate with neighborhood community centers or business incubators that serve as hubs for entrepreneurs to obtain technology, network, and learn (Khalid & Baharudin, 2021).

Using the assistance of well-organized processes and readily available educational materials, this approach can help B40 entrepreneurs in Kelantan receive the skills and self-assurance they need to prosper in the digital economy. Participants in the e-module affiliate program can increase the visibility and reach of their businesses while earning a steady income.

3. FINDINGS

The E-Modul Affiliate Program demonstrates significant potential to empower B40 entrepreneurs in Kelantan by enhancing their digital marketing capabilities. As digital marketing becomes increasingly vital for business growth, equipping low-income entrepreneurs with the necessary skills and knowledge is essential for economic empowerment and sustained success.

The generally low level of digital literacy among Kelantan's B40 entrepreneurs is a significant finding in evaluating their preparedness for affiliate programs and digital marketing. This income category includes many entrepreneurs who lack a basic understanding of social media, technological advances, and digital marketing approaches. Their lack of ability to fully participate in the digital economy is a result of this weakness. B40 entrepreneurs were surveyed and interviewed, and the results showed that although many of them had access to mobile devices, they were not familiar with fundamental features like using affiliate marketing tools, creating content, or setting up business accounts.

Access to technology and a stable internet connection emerged as a significant challenge for B40 entrepreneurs, especially those in rural areas of Kelantan. The infrastructure, such as high-speed internet, was not uniformly available to support consistent online marketing efforts. Furthermore, many entrepreneurs did not have access to computers or laptops, relying exclusively on smartphones. This limits the range of digital marketing tools they can use, particularly those that are more efficiently managed via desktop devices.

4. DISCUSSION

Through the e-module affiliate program, B40 (bottom 40% income group) entrepreneurs in Kelantan are empowered to use digital marketing, which is an effective method for encouraging growth in the economy. By empowering low-income people to promote things online, this strategy uses digital resources and affiliate marketing techniques to generate revenue opportunities for them. Digital marketing offers an accessible, cost-effective way for B40 entrepreneurs to expand their businesses and reach a broader customer base. Digital networks like Facebook, Instagram, and e-commerce sites like Shopee and Lazada allow business owners to advertise their goods for little to no cost. This eliminates the need for B40 business owners to pay for physical space rentals and lowers marketing expenses.

By using digital platforms, these entrepreneurs can advertise to more customers. Without having sufficient inventory, they can generate additional income streams by promoting the goods of other businesses and earning commissions through affiliate marketing. B40 entrepreneurs can promote

products from well-known companies and earn fees by participating in affiliate programs provided by websites such as Lazada, and Shopee. They can use blogs, social media, and other online channels for this. By providing an e-module, which is a structured online learning module, entrepreneurs can learn how to engage in affiliate marketing effectively. The e-module provides lessons on how to set up affiliate accounts, promote products using social media, and use tracking tools to monitor sales and commissions.

Despite the opportunities that digital marketing presents, there are several challenges B40 entrepreneurs in Kelantan face which is Digital literacy may be low among many B40 entrepreneurs, particularly those in rural areas. Because of this, it could be challenging for them to use online platforms and marketing tools or understand affiliate marketing's intricate details. In rural areas, access to computers, smartphones, and dependable internet connectivity is frequently limited. Despite the widespread usage of smartphones, inadequate internet speeds or expensive data plans may make it difficult for users to engage in digital marketing activities.

By empowering B40 entrepreneurs in Kelantan through the e-module affiliate program, there is potential for significant economic and social impact as entrepreneurs may experience an increase in income from both their own product sales and affiliate commissions if they successfully implement the skills learned through the e-module and affiliate programs. Digital marketing can help reduce poverty and raise living standards by giving B40 entrepreneurs a reliable source of income. The transition to digital entrepreneurship may also open new doors for women and younger members of the B40 group, which will promote youth and gender empowerment. Kelantan's indigenous goods, including handicrafts and traditional delicious foods, can reach bigger, even global markets as more entrepreneurs use digital marketing. Online sales can support the preservation of culture and a stronger local economy.

5. CONCLUSION

The results show that affiliate programs combined with digital marketing may significantly improve the income of Kelantan's B40 entrepreneurs. However, to fulfill this opportunity to the fullest, issues including low digital literacy, and access to technology to be resolved. Although the E-Modul Affiliate Program is a useful instrument for developing fundamental skills, more work is required to guarantee long-term success and sustainability. Future B40 entrepreneurs in Kelantan will need ongoing assistance, skill development, and cooperation from the public, commercial, and community sectors to achieve sustainable digital transformation. This e-module strategy can act as a scalable model for empowering low-income entrepreneurs throughout Malaysia and related locations, ultimately promoting inclusive economic development by building on the fundamental success of the E-Modul Affiliate Program. The E-Modul Affiliate Program is a great step towards empowering Kelantan's B40 entrepreneurs. With an emphasis on affiliate marketing and digital marketing, this program gives entrepreneurs the know-how and abilities they need to succeed in the digital economy. This project, which tackles important issues including market access, financial constraints, and digital literacy, has the potential to bring out sustainable socioeconomic change in the area. Utilizing digital empowerment, B40 entrepreneurs might overcome traditional obstacles and use innovative customers, to promote financial stability and expansion within Kelantan. With carefully developed training materials, affiliate program access, and continuous assistance, the program provides entrepreneurs the opportunity to promote products online, expand their customer base, and bring in additional income. Moreover, the initiative supports a more inclusive, scalable type of entrepreneurship that can lower poverty and enhance livelihoods by utilizing partnerships, coaching, and low-cost technology solutions.

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